

UNCERTAINTY MANAGEMENT FOR TEAMS:
THE STRATEGY OF DEVELOPING SHARED UNDERSTANDING
IN THE FACE OF UNCERTAINTY

FINAL REPORT

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ISSUES AND OBJECTIVES

It is widely recognized that the ongoing revolution in information technologies is driving unparalleled changes in military operations. Military leaders have regarded superior information and communications as critical determinants of victory throughout history. Yet, the current unprecedented rate of change in information capabilities demands that the information domain be scrutinized more intensely than ever. This is necessary in part to mitigate the risk that advances will outstrip our ability to generate, develop, and implement truly beneficial operational concepts (Joint Vision 2020, 2003).

It is paramount that two interrelated principles be kept in mind in developing new information technologies to support human decision making. First, information superiority does not presume perfect information, or that the “fog of war” will be eliminated. That is, the human agents in the system will always be forced to decide and execute while experiencing some degree of uncertainty in the appropriateness of their chosen courses of action. No technology can change that basic fact.

Second, information superiority reflects far more than the accumulation of more or better information than one’s adversary. At this point, the critical bottleneck in turning information into competitive advantage is in the cognitive processes that lead to human understanding. One approach to dealing with this situation is to attempt to develop technologies that automatically transform raw data into understanding, so that it will be available to key decision makers (e.g., Fleming, n.d.). This general approach is based on a popular sequential stage model of understanding that suggests a mechanical transformation of raw data at the bottom through stages of information and knowledge that finally ends at understanding (e.g., Alberts, 2001). Discussion of this model always implies that the level of understanding rests within the automated processing and display of the data. Hence, understanding is assumed to be something that resides outside of human decision makers and that can be directly transmitted to them. This model and approach fails to appreciate that understanding does not lie within the technology. This is important to acknowledge for a number of reasons, including that the approach can actually increase the individual’s uncertainty in his or her understanding by cutting out too many “low-level” facts. In this case, people can be expected to reject or work around the technology.

The above principles imply that care must be taken in developing conceptual models and new technologies to ensure that they give due consideration to the human cognitive requirements of the system. They also imply that there is a basic need to understand the sources of human uncertainty and how they are managed in order to provide better direction for future technological development.

The primary goal of the current research and development effort is to provide the Navy with a collaborative tool that supports the development of shared understanding within distributed, asynchronous, and multicultural intelligence analyst teams. This Phase I effort focused on three specific objectives in support of the overall goal, and each has been successfully accomplished:

1. Developed and conducted initial tests of a cognitive process-based model that describes how teams develop a shared understanding in the face of uncertainty.
2. Derived requirements from the model for tools that will aid in the development of shared understanding.
3. Generated specific collaborative tool and metrics concepts to support and assess shared understanding development, based on the cognitive model and implied requirements.

In the Phase I option period, we will accomplish two additional objectives:

1. Create initial prototypes of the tool and metrics concepts for baseline testing in Phase II.
2. Design field experiments that will be conducted in Phase II to test the added value of the collaborative tool and metrics concepts.

Our Phase I results mark a substantial conceptual advancement for the Collaboration and Knowledge Management program, and the Navy. Phase II will provide validated tools that support the development of shared understanding by distributed, asynchronous intelligence analysis teams. We have already received expressions of interest in collaborating on the Phase II effort from the Institute for Human and Machine Cognition, who have considerable expertise in developing concept mapping tools, and the NSA has also expressed interest in solutions resulting from our efforts.

OVERVIEW OF RESEARCH ACTIVITIES

Our overall Phase I research strategy was to collect incidents involving team uncertainty management from a diverse set of domains. This breadth was intended to permit the development of a robust, domain-general model. In subsequent applications, model details can be specified for particular domains or situations. At the core of our methodologies were Cognitive Task Analysis (CTA) interviews and naturalistic observations. The purpose of the CTA interviews was to elicit the cognitive and decision-making processes underlying subject-matter experts' (SMEs) actual team uncertainty experiences. The incident accounts of these experiences form the core of our data for model development. Over the course of the Phase I effort, we developed and iteratively refined a CTA interview guide specifically designed to uncover cognitive aspects underlying the development of team understanding in the face of uncertainty. This "Interview Guide for Team Development of Shared Understanding" is provided in Appendix 1.

The primary data collection activities included an initial wave of interviews with SMEs from a variety of backgrounds. This initial wave was followed by a data collection trip to the Joint Forces Intelligence Command, where we interviewed several SMEs in the intelligence analysis domain. We also observed a large scale, multi-agency exercise on emergency response to weapons of mass destruction, reviewed and analyzed Klein Associates' archival data pertaining to team uncertainty management, and conducted a

review of pertinent literature primarily focused on group decision making and group forecasting.

The information we collected during this period has led to initial formation and iterative development of our theoretical and practical tool concepts. In the subsequent sections, we describe the state of our thinking on the issues and remaining questions as they exist at the conclusion of the Phase I period.

UNCERTAINTY MANAGEMENT FOR TEAMS

The current study stemmed from the basic need to understand the sources of team uncertainty and strategies by which they are managed in order to provide direction for collaborative technology development. An initial lead on this issue was provided by Schmitt and Klein (1996). Specifically, Schmitt and Klein conducted a study examining uncertainty management by individual Marine commanders. From these observations, they identified four causes of uncertainty: missing or unavailable information, unreliable or low-credibility information, ambiguous and conflicting information, and complex information. In this study, ambiguous and conflicting information accounted for approximately 50% of the incidents of uncertainty the researchers observed. This finding is especially important because a common assumption is that uncertainty is due to missing information. So most technology solutions emphasize ways of increasing the amount of information presented, which tends to increase the amount of ambiguous and conflicting information. As will be seen, ambiguous and conflicting information is especially pertinent in team uncertainty situations. In particular, conflicting mental models among team members appear to provide an especially important source of team uncertainty.

In addition to the types of uncertainty, Schmitt and Klein (1996) identified three levels of uncertainty: level of data, level of knowledge, and level of understanding (cf. Endsley, 1995). The level of data consists of uncertainty about factual information. The level of knowledge is the level at which individuals draw inferences from the data. Finally, the level of understanding is the level at which these inferences are used to create projections about the future, explanations about events, and identifications of critical vulnerabilities. Effective commanders reduce their uncertainty by spending time integrating and drawing meaning from the existing data rather than seeking more data. This implies a need for training or technology that encourages integration activities. Technologies that “take over” active integration bypass the cognitive needs of experts and thereby leave them with greater feelings of uncertainty.

An additional exploratory study of the nature of uncertainty faced by Marine Corps warfighters was conducted by McCloskey (1996). In his study, McCloskey used two dimensions for classifying uncertainty: sources of uncertainty and levels at which uncertainty can exist. To develop the sources of uncertainty, McCloskey reviewed narratives in which historical military commanders were faced with uncertain situations on the battlefield. McCloskey and his team also observed a five-day Marine exercise at Twentynine Palms, California, where they observed and recorded almost 100 instances

in which command post staff members were faced with uncertainty. Four primary sources of uncertainty emerged for battlefield decision makers: missing information, unreliable information, ambiguous/conflicting information, and complexity. As in the Schmitt & Klein study, uncertainty due to ambiguous/conflicting information predominated.

The above studies focused on uncertainty experienced by individuals. Sources of uncertainty for teams have been studied in a quite different domain, that of patient resuscitation (Xiao & Mackenzie, 1997) . In this study, case segments involving trauma patient resuscitations were analyzed to try to understand how various types of uncertainty arise during the initial stages of resuscitation. Specifically, over 40 case segments were analyzed, with the intention of answering the question of, “What is uncertain to the team specifically related to the case segment?” Some items, such as the patient’s prior medical history, concerned the resuscitation task itself; however, others were related to team and organizational factors. These included: the lack of extensive standard operating procedures, observed procedures changing from one leading surgeon to the next, duplicate execution of tasks, critical tasks unattended, and lack of communication of key information. The notion that team uncertainty can arise from the task or from team coordination issues appears repeatedly in our investigations, and is incorporated as a fundamental aspect of our model.

In the above studies, the primary source of uncertainty appears to be conflicting or ambiguous information, and team uncertainty results from underlying issues residing in the task or the team. In addition to classifications of the sources of uncertainty, one can also consider distinct ways in which individuals and teams can cope or deal with the uncertainty. For example, Schmitt and Klein (1996) described how, in the face of uncertainty, people can engage in a range of different strategies: delay making a decision until the situation becomes clearer, actively seek more information, fill gaps with assumptions, press on regardless, take actions that will structure the situation, simplify the plan, prepare for the worst case, or make incremental decisions that can be adapted in light of feedback.

At the team level, there are at least two primary ways in which uncertainty resulting from conflicting understanding among team members can be dealt with. The first is to “close off” team members who are adding additional uncertainty. The second is to attempt to develop a shared understanding among team members, and thereby reduce the uncertainty. As an example of the first way, consider the case of a Fire Chief who became the Incident Commander at a Weapons of Mass Destruction (WMD) exercise (see Table 1).

Table 1

Incident Command vs. Incident Commander

Greene County's emergency management had been handled by Dayton up until about two years prior to their first major exercise. The exercise entailed a response to a Weapons of Mass Destruction event. First a train derailed, and a chlorine gas cloud emanated from the area. There were about 20 victims on a nearby soccer field; they were "walking wounded." Then a car that was speeding away from the area wrecked. The driver and a policeman were killed, and a possible initiation device was found. Many agencies have to coordinate to deal with this kind of event and had representatives on the scene, including multiple fire and police departments, EMS, FBI, Wright Patterson Air Force Base, Greene County Health Department, the Army Bomb Squad, and the Ohio EPA. (This is not a complete list.) A Fairborn Fire Chief took command of the situation from a reasonably nearby sports complex, the Nutter Center. He became the Incident Commander, and set up the Emergency Operations Center (EOC) on a deck outside the Nutter Center. The EOC consists of many key decision makers, including among others, county commissioners and mayors, who are needed to permit critical actions taken within their jurisdictions. To the Chief's surprise, shortly after he set up the EOC and became engaged coordinating with operations and many others, these key decision makers had tables moved into the Nutter Center and went inside. This was clearly baffling to the guys on the deck, but events were moving too fast to straighten it out. The Chief had a runner check in with the splintered EOC group several times early on, but the coordination costs were too high. He thus "wrote off" the rest of the EOC early on, and simply cut them out of the loop. At the after action review, it appeared that the split may have been due to definitional problems, with some people believing that the EOC was separate from an Incident Command, as opposed to the Incident Commander being in charge of the EOC. In a follow-up interview, the Chief noted that this kind of thing could easily happen in a real situation.

The ways of dealing with team uncertainty such as that taken by the Incident Commander are quite interesting and important for a comprehensive theoretical treatment of team uncertainty management. However, the remainder of this report will focus instead on the second means of reducing uncertainty, with an aim towards achieving sufficient depth on that strategy to enable the near-term development of practical solutions. Specifically, we will focus on situations where teams manage uncertainty emerging from the conflicting views of individual members by attempting to develop a shared understanding of the situation. Based on interview information and observations, we will develop a cognitive model of the natural processes involved, and propose specific collaborative tool and metrics concepts based on the model.

THE DEVELOPMENT OF SHARED UNDERSTANDING IN THE FACE OF UNCERTAINTY

Shared Mental Models: To Have or To Develop?

As an initial step in considering the strategy of developing a shared understanding, we examine whether it is better to have a shared understanding from the onset, or to be able to efficiently come to one from divergent backgrounds. Two strands of research that have addressed this issue appear to provide discrepant conclusions on this issue at a surface level. Mathieu, Goodwin, Heffner, Salas, and Cannon-Bowers (Mathieu, Goodwin, Heffner, Salas, & Cannon-Bowers, 2000) describe Shared Mental Model Theory as one that explains how teams are able to cope with difficult and changing conditions. Mental models are defined as organized knowledge structures that allow individuals to predict and explain the behavior of the world around them, to recognize relationships, and to predict events in their environment. Shared mental models enable team members to select courses of action that are coordinated with those of their teammates.

The purpose of their study was to measure the extent to which teammates share different types of mental models, and to determine the relationship of that sharedness to indices of team process and performance. They specifically proposed the following hypotheses:

1. Task related mental models and team related mental models can be assessed and are tapping qualitatively different processes.
2. Shared mental models (both task and team) would relate significantly to team processes including communication processes, strategy and coordinated use of resources, and cooperation.
3. Team processes would relate significantly to team performance, mediating the influence of shared mental models on team performance.
4. With increased experience with teammates and the task, team members' mental models would develop greater convergence, thereby leading to better team processes and performance.

In order to test these hypotheses, the researchers used a low-fidelity personal-computer-based flight simulator task. The teams were dyads, and each team had different roles. Following training on the task, the teams completed three performance trials. The researchers measured team performance on the task, team process on three dimensions (strategy formation and coordination, cooperation, and communication), task mental models and team mental models, and mental model centrality and convergence. Task and team mental models were assessed using teammates' individual ratings of the relationships between various attributes. Mental model centrality and convergence were measured using a network-analysis program. In their experiment, Mathieu et al. (2000) uncovered several interesting findings:

- The two mental model convergence indices did not correlate significantly, providing evidence that the two types of mental models (task and team) are tapping different processes.
- Sharedness of team mental models was related significantly to performance, but the relationship was mediated by team processes.
- Sharedness of task mental models was not related significantly to performance, but did relate to team processes, thus *indirectly* influencing team performance.
- There was no increase in mental model sharedness (for task or team mental models) over time, as hypothesized. The researchers believe this may be due to the fact that they did not offer any developmental feedback after each performance trial, such as pointing out errors and offering suggestions.
- There was significant improvement in team process (coordinating, strategizing, and cooperating) over time.

Given the link between mental model sharedness, team process, and resulting performance, the authors suggest that mental model sharedness in teams be enhanced. One specific recommendation is to initially select team members who possess highly overlapping mental models. Hence, these researchers clearly suggest that the ideal is for team members to possess highly similar mental models from the outset.

Research involving a quite different paradigm suggests just the opposite conclusion; i.e., that initially divergent mental models can be quite useful in the collaborative construction of a comprehensive picture of a situation (Gettys, Pliske, Manning, & Casey, 1987). For example, in a study by Gettys et al., people were asked to individually generate potential solutions to a parking crisis, and then to estimate the number of options they had missed in terms of options that others might have considered. The individual solutions were compared to those generated by the group as a whole, and there were far more solutions generated by the group. The net gain in solutions generated stems from the fact that the individual's task mental models diverged considerably. This finding suggests that, to the extent that team members are able to develop a shared understanding based on very distinctive individual mental models, the team's understanding has the potential to be quite comprehensive. Indeed, the gains tend to be greater than the individuals actually expect. This is supported by the finding that the study participants dramatically underestimated the number of solutions they had missed (Gettys et al., 1987). That is, in tasks such as that employed by Gettys et al., people tend to overestimate the extent to which others share a common understanding of the world. As an aside, there is often a focus on developing metrics for shared awareness or shared understanding. This latter finding implies that there is also considerable potential value in *metacognitive* metrics to assess individual team members' awareness of the extent to which their mental models overlap.

These results of Gettys, et al. (1987) appear in stark contrast with those of Mathieu et al. (2000), and support the idea that individual mental models among team members would most usefully be quite divergent, and that efficient processes for developing a shared understanding should be preferred to possession of shared mental models from the outset. However, note that Mathieu et al. utilized a task with an extremely short decision cycle

time (flight coordination), whereas Gettys et al. utilized a task where the decision cycle would be much longer. Indeed, a full decision was not actually required in the span of their study (only the generation of possible parking solutions), in contrast with many quick decisions being made in the flight coordination task. These results and observations suggest that shared mental models are required at the onset to manage tasks with extremely short decision cycle times, but that decisions with longer cycles allow for the benefits associated with initially divergent mental models.

Situational Constraints on the Strategy of Developing Shared Understanding

As exemplified in the preceding discussion, there are several situational characteristics that influence how teams respond to uncertainty, as well as how they should respond. The Collaborative Knowledge Management (CKM) framework provides guidance on specific characteristics that affect team collaboration in general. The most crucial characteristic encountered in the current research was the decision cycle time. In those situations where decisions had to be made extremely quickly, the cognitive demands largely reflected high needs for multi-tasking. Furthermore, in these situations the primary strategy for handling team uncertainty was to “close out” team members, such as was used by the Incident Commander in the WMD example presented above. Another example with a short decision cycle time is presented in Table 2 and Figure 1, below. This example highlights the high cognitive load due to multi-tasking, particularly because of demands to communicate with many parties while attempting to diagnose a specific problem.

In contrast, situations involving longer decision cycles allow members to focus on the development of shared understanding. Teams in these situations still appear to feel time pressured, and clearly experience significant cognitive demands. However, the nature of the demands is quite different. Specifically, they largely involve memory management issues such as those stemming from requirements to keep in mind one’s own understanding of the situation, while attempting to digest and critically evaluate other members’ ideas. Given that decision cycle time, in particular, leads to distinctive cognitive processing and associated demands, we restricted our attention to those situations involving longer decision cycles wherein teams are most likely to attempt to develop a collective understanding.

Table 2

Chill Water Incident

Electronics on a ship must have chill water, kept at 40-50 degrees in order to survive. If the systems are not kept cool they will be damaged. In this incident, a ship had developed a pin sized hole in a pipe of a chill water loop. Proper procedures had not been followed for repairing it because it was too difficult to access and was obscured by the complexity of the pipes. Over the course of time, the pin sized hole developed into a crack, opened, and eventually started spraying water onto an electrical distribution panel.

While this happened, the DCA (Damage Control Assistant) of the ship was within fifty feet of the chill line. He needed to decide whether or not to stay to fix the damage, or return to DC (Damage Control) Central so that he could carry out his duties and coordinate everyone in the event. He decided to stay with the crew at the site for a short time to try to isolate the leak. When access to the leak could not be obtained, it was decided that the power distribution panel should be shielded to minimize additional complications. Shortly after, the At Sea Fire Party was called upon. There were two inches of water on the deck by the time they had arrived. When they, too, were unsuccessful at stopping the leak, additional personnel were called upon. They also were unsuccessful.

At the same time the At Sea Fire Party showed up, the DCA went to DC Central to establish communication with the people at the scene. He and the Chief Engineer pulled out the chill water references to determine a way to isolate the break. At the same time this was happening, the CSMC (Combat Systems Maintenance Center) reported that there was low pressure in the entire chill water system. This meant that the AEGIS system was close to being damaged because it was not being kept cool. The decision was made to take AEGIS off line, though it would leave the ship blind and unable to perform its mission.

During the situation, the DCA and Chief Engineer continued to try to find a way to isolate the leak; eventually the entire contents of the chill water line emptied out onto the deck.

At the time of the incident, the DCA was convinced he had the best information. However, he later learned that a valve that had been reported closed was actually open even though lots of people were being sent out to check on and close the valves. In the mean time, he and the Chief Engineer were tracing pipes with their fingers to determine where the leak could be coming from, while continuing to give reports to those on scene on what they were seeing, hearing, and what attempts were being made to isolate the leak. He was also communicating with the bridge since they were about to go blind with the AEGIS system ready to be shut off.

Figure 1. Chill water: Event sequence.

The Development of Shared Understanding in Group Decision Making: Performance and Prescription

Most research in decision making assumes relatively long decision cycle times, and the issue of how teams develop a shared understanding in the face of uncertainty is directly related to research on group decision making, especially group forecasting. Hence, we might expect that literature to inform our model development. In initially examining the judgment and decision literature on these topics, we found that there is a considerable emphasis on judgmental forecasting accuracy. For example, an issue of importance might be whether a single expert's forecast will be better or worse than the aggregate opinions of a number of experts. It seems intuitively obvious that the collection of experts should generate a better forecast than an individual, since the group must possess at least the same amount of knowledge as its most knowledgeable member. Empirical studies have thus attempted to determine the relative merits of group vs. individual procedures. In a typical study, the judgments of individual group members are first collected. Then, the individuals are placed in interacting groups where they arrive at collective judgments. The average accuracy of individual judgments is then compared with the group accuracy. In these kinds of studies across a range of tasks, group judgment has typically been found to be more accurate than individual judgment (Hill, 1982). A related issue is whether the

group's judgments are more accurate than that of the best member, and some studies have found that to be the case (e.g., Sniezek & Henry, 1989). However, groups more commonly fail to meet this higher performance standard (Hill, 1982; Miner, 1984). Research in this vein has also been conducted on biases in group decision making, most prominently "groupthink," in which highly cohesive teams avoid exploring divergent points of view in order to preserve the harmony of the group (Janis, 1972; Park, 1990). There is also substantial evidence indicating the existence of a "shared information effect." That is, rather than describing the divergent aspects of their mental models, groups will tend to talk about those aspects that they all share (Christensen et al., 2000). As with groupthink, the shared information effect reduces the chances that divergent aspects of mental models will be brought to light. In contrast, other biases emphasize polarization, for instance, when individuals intensify conflict for purposes that do not directly serve group aims, such as seeking to avoid losing face (Hoffman, 1965).

Some research has been conducted to determine team characteristics that separate highly and poorly performing teams. The idea is that, by instructing teams to adopt characteristics associated with high team performance, the judgment and decision performance will improve. For example, the Advanced Team Decision Making (ATDM) model contains ten behaviors that gauge a team's success (Zsombok, Klein, Kyne, & Klinger, 1992). The ATDM model is applicable for strategic and tactical teams as well as planning and action teams. The ten behaviors are organized within three team elements: team identity, team self monitoring, and team conceptual level. The ATDM model could be a valuable tool for assessing team performance by providing ready metrics for team functioning. However, it and other performance models of teamwork do not address the processes by which team collaboration occurs.

The bulk of research in the area of group decision making has focused on the development of structured group techniques to improve performance (G. Rowe, 1998). The underlying assumption driving the development of such methods is typically to raise performance levels by reducing aspects of the group decision making that have been associated with bias. The group environment is thus structured to limit possible negative social influences, but to still allow some form of group interaction to take place so as to promote knowledge synthesis. One example is "electronic brainstorming." In electronic brainstorming team members enter their ideas anonymously into networked computers, where they appear to all of the team members (Gallupe & Cooper, 1993). Research has shown that participants produce more ideas since they are less inhibited when using electronic, as compared with conventional, face-to-face brainstorming. The electronic version of brainstorming also aids with the team's memory management, since members can enter their ideas simultaneously, rather than having to wait for their turn to talk.

Probably the most well-known approach to group decision making is the Delphi method (Dalkey & Helmer, 1963; G. Rowe, Wright, & Bolger, 1991). In addition to attempting to limit group biases, the nature of the Delphi method allows for many participants. The Delphi method is characterized by four features: anonymity, controlled feedback, iteration over multiple rounds, and statistical aggregation to arrive at a group response.

In the basic procedure, an initial unstructured round is conducted in which individual experts can identify and elaborate on issues that they see as important. The issues are all consolidated by the facilitators into a set of items that require quantitative judgments. Individual group members report their judgments privately by responding to questionnaires that list the items. The results of the expressed opinions are pooled and then provided as feedback to individual respondents. The individuals are then able to respond again to the questionnaires in light of the current feedback, and so change their answers in light of the group's "beliefs." Also, if their judgments are far off from the central tendency of the group, then individual experts may be asked to supply reasons why they believe their selection is correct against the majority. These (anonymous) reasons would then be supplied to all of the experts. The process iterates until the judgments stabilize over time, and ideally, opinions converge.

A fundamental issue concerning the Delphi method is the nature of its actual purpose (G. Rowe, 1998). One possibility is that the fundamental aim is to provide a means for achieving consensus. Another is that the aim is instead to improve judgment. Other issues concern whether it actually achieves either of these objectives, and to what extent the fundamental assumptions on which it is based are actually sound. For example, comparisons between Delphi and unstructured interacting groups have yielded mixed results (G. Rowe, 1998). One potential reason that the Delphi method may not clearly outperform natural group processes is that the natural groups do quite well. Consider Table 3, which shows for example, how at least one group of intelligence analysts yielded forecasts, and evidence that their consensus was in fact quite good.

In sum, the focus in much of the literature on group decision making and group forecasting has been on performance and prescribed processes. Furthermore, many of the prescribed structured group processes are predicated on the assumption that the natural processes are flawed. Hence, they attempt to alter and constrain the process in specific ways that attempt to promote an objective focus on the substantive issues. Surprisingly, little work has yet been done on understanding the mechanisms underlying the natural collaborative process. Without such an understanding, it is difficult to know what effects prescriptions such as the Delphi method actually have, including any important aspects of the natural process that are lost.

Table 3

Mirror Imaging Incident

The incident took place in the mid-1980s, before the Soviet collapse. Every year or so, the USAF would come out with a large document predicting what the Russians would be building for the coming twelve years. The estimates were used to figure out how much we should build, for arms negotiations, etc. Analysts at two different organizations would generate estimates for the same quantities (300-400 total number of estimates for each organization, if count estimate for each year separately). One group was in Omaha, and the other group was in Washington DC. The two groups had no real personal contact.

Within the Omaha group, the team consisted of three people. They were assigned the task from a commander. They divided up the set of estimates (e.g., you take the bombers, I'll take the fighters), and worked through them. There was some math behind it, but in the end their estimates came from analytical judgment. They talked about their estimates within their small team, at least informally, and they achieved pretty smooth agreement amongst themselves (e.g., Lean over to next desk—"hey does this look all right to you for fighters?" "Yeah, sure.").

They submitted their estimates to their commander. The DC group had to do all the same estimates. The Omaha and DC groups' estimates were then compared at the command level. For all the ones that contained small discrepancies, the commanders might average the two estimates, or maybe just pick one to get the final number. Out of the full set, only about a dozen were widely different and so drew further scrutiny.

In general, there was no firm procedure for handling the discrepant cases. The commanders would likely double back with their analysts and request a rationale. They might just ask the analysts to recheck those numbers or answer the question, "Why do you think this?" without providing any further information. Or, they might ask the analysts to justify their estimate as compared with the other group's estimate (e.g., "Why are they so far off?"). The commanders might swap rationales. Sometimes the analysts would see the other side's rationale, but not necessarily. The commanders might just decide who to believe based on the rationales provided.

The interviewee recalled one estimate in particular that was way off, having to do with tankers. The Russians had just finished a new facility for building tankers, and the AF analysts were estimating the number of tankers that the Russians would build. The Omaha group hypothesized that they would build less than a hundred, maybe 67 or so. However, the DC group hypothesized that the Russians would build hundreds of them.

The commander told the Omaha group the DC group's estimate, and asked them to explain why the two were so far off. The Omaha group's reasoning included that:

1. We studied their ops, and they wouldn't make that many- the Russians have always had a smaller force than we do.
2. The Russians have insufficient resources to build many tankers.
3. The Russians do not have the infrastructure to support that many tankers.

The Omaha group believed that the DC group was reasoning based on how the US would do it. Putting the new facility in place, they would naturally build hundreds of tankers, because that's what we would do. That is, they felt the DC group was relying on a mirror imaging assumption—inappropriately assuming that the other culture's C2 would behave the same way as the U.S.'s would. However, because they did not communicate directly with the Omaha group, they never really found out what that sides' reasoning was.

A Cognitive Process Model of Shared Understanding Development

Teams are generally comprised of individuals with an array of backgrounds, an array of experiences, and different levels of expertise. As a result of these different backgrounds and different depths and ranges of experience, each team member possesses a unique repertoire of mental models, which affect which data he or she notices and considers, and how those data are interpreted. Because of these different mental models, even if team members consider the same data, they may interpret that data quite differently. To the extent that they are considering distinct information, the potential for differences in individual team member mental models is even greater.

We next turn to describing a novel model that describes the cognitive processes underlying team members' efforts to develop a shared understanding. A flow diagram of the major model elements is shown in Figure 2. Table 4 provides an example that illustrates the various aspects of the model. The example is referred to repeatedly in the following description of the stages.

Figure 2. A model of shared understanding development

Table 4

Uncommanded Pitch Incident

The incident occurred with one of the C141s while coming in for landing. The plane had an “uncommanded pitch problem” - the nose suddenly started to rise and the pilot had to force it down to get it on the ground. This was a serious event—the plane could easily have crashed. Naturally, this was a huge concern to the pilot and flight crew.

The plane was impounded, and a Tiger Team was formed to determine the cause and repair it. The Tiger Team included Electronics, Avionics/guidance control, Aero repair, and Hydraulics specialists. The Tiger Team was led by the Manager of Aircraft Maintenance Technicians. He was the official decision maker in the incident. The Manager also had the flight chief, a senior enlisted man, available as an advisor.

The team performed checks on individual systems, discussed inter-system problems, and tried to determine the cause. They performed check after check, but couldn’t find anything wrong. This went on for several days. At that point, they had a team meeting to try to figure out what was going on, and determine what they were going to do. The meeting turned into a heated discussion. Although multiple theories were discussed, the debate appeared centered between two groups. The first group included those who felt the problem should be written up as a “cannot duplicate,” and thereby sending the plane back up, and the second group consisted of those who felt that they had to do something.

Several of the specialists wanted to write the incident off as a “cannot duplicate,” and send the plane back up. These members said things like, “you know what, we can’t duplicate it, there’s nothing we can do, we’re done, we feel confident we have checked everything we can check, the airplane is good. It was just a glitch that happened and never would happen again.” There were others who said, “that’s not good enough. I don’t want it on my conscience that this airplane crashes on its very next flight, that we did nothing.” And this is not going to be good enough for the ops guys. If we tell them it is ok, they are going to tell us—no it isn’t.” Those in this group wanted to take some maintenance action, based on a best guess. The manager sided with this group from the beginning.

The team discussed multiple possible theories. The kinds of theories that they generated tended to justify the class of action they wanted to take. For example, the “can’t duplicate” group cited wind sheer and dirty hydraulics as possible reasons for the experience. Wind sheer meant a fluke event, and dirt in the hydraulics is something that would have worked itself out of the system. Hence, no action would be required in either case. On the other hand, the “take an action” group proposed electrical relays or a bad PTA as the potential causes. For both of these possible sources, the problem was real and would replicate in the air, but would not present in the on the ground tests. The stress of real flight was needed for these problems to surface.

In the end, the manager felt the most likely cause was electrical relays. It struck him that the relays were as old as he was. He had also developed rebuttals for all of the other theories, including those that implied it as a fluke event (e.g., wind sheer should push the nose up, not down). Interestingly, he had clearly thought through details of all of the theories on his own with some level of depth. And he had been involved hands-on in the checks and rechecks from the start of the incident. Yet, ultimately he said he was really looking at his flight chief, his senior enlisted guy who’s been around the block for quite a while, to guide his understanding of the problem, and following decision.

The electrical relays were replaced, the plane was flight tested, checked out and was sent back up. It has not been a problem since. The manager recognized that they would never really know if the relays were the source of the problem, or if it was just a fluke.

Underlying Task or Team Issue

As shown in Figure 2, the development of shared understanding begins with an underlying issue. As discussed previously, the issue may have to do with either the task or with the internal functioning of the team. For example, Mathieu et al. (2000) described four types of shared mental models:

1. Technology/equipment mental models – describe and organize knowledge pertaining to things like equipment functioning, operating procedures, system limitations, etc.
2. Job/task mental models – organize knowledge about how the task is accomplished in terms of procedures, task strategies, likely contingencies or problems, and environmental conditions.
3. Team interaction mental models– knowledge about team members’ roles and responsibilities, interaction patterns, information flow and communication channels, role interdependencies, and information sources.
4. Team mental models – knowledge specific to the strengths, weaknesses, knowledge, skills, attitudes, preferences, etc. of one’s teammates.

However, the four-part scheme can be reduced into two overarching types of mental models: 1) task related mental models; and 2) team related mental models. Discrepancies could exist for each of these kinds of mental models, leading to the potential for emergent collective uncertainty among the team.

In the case of the uncommanded pitch, the instigating issue stems from the conflicting information that the flight crew reported a serious error, but that repeated testing resulted in no diagnosed problems. Here, the discrepancy exists among the team members’ task related mental models, in that they each have distinct accounts that serve to explain the information conflict. Note that the development of shared understanding occurs in this case as a result of the mental model differences, not the original information conflict. If all the team members held the same explanation for the information conflict initially, it would be unnecessary for the team to develop their shared understanding. Indeed, the common view would likely serve to increase individual members’ certainty in their understanding, so that no development of understanding would be deemed necessary in any case.

Surprise/Anomaly Surfaces and Team Uncertainty Emerges

An underlying issue may exist for some time without notice, but eventually surfaces as a surprise, an anomaly, or a violation of expectations that leads to a moment of emergent uncertainty. At this point, at least some members of the team begin to question their joint interpretation of the situation.

If the discrepancy pertains to the team related mental models, then the issue is a fundamental breakdown in common ground. As defined by Klein, Feltoovich, Bradshaw, and Woods (2004), common ground refers to the pertinent mutual knowledge, mutual

beliefs, and mutual assumptions that support interdependent actions in some joint activity. In the fundamental common ground breakdown, one party defects from the group's joint activity and leaves the other parties believing that everything is proceeding as normal. That is, the team dynamics have changed, but at least some team members have not been informed. An example of a fundamental common ground breakdown was the difference in team understanding between the Incident Commander and the rest of the members of the Emergency Operations Center from the WMD Exercise incident presented in Table 1.

Team Resolution Process

This moment of uncertainty may lead the team to engage in a conscious and deliberate process in which team members share and attempt to integrate their individual mental models so as to develop a new or revised understanding of the situation. In the resolution process, team members produce and consume fragments of each other's mental models. This production and consumption of mental model fragments manifests itself as the generation and sharing of arguments, rebuttals, and counterarguments among team members. By arguments, we mean statements that imply a movement from initial facts to a final claim.

One critical assumption of the shared understanding model is that the arguments do not necessarily have to do with substantive beliefs about the world. They can also reflect the person's values or goals. Indeed, we do not see people clearly separating beliefs and values, but rather intermixing the two routinely. If anything, it appears as if team members attempt to establish and discuss their values for particular outcomes first, and then constrain their search for theories to belief based on desired outcomes.

For example, in the uncommanded pitch incident, the merits of reporting a "cannot duplicate" versus "switching out a candidate component" were deeply intertwined with diagnostic judgments, and they also appeared to precede the generation and discussion of specific substantive theories.

This part of the example also illustrates another aspect of developing shared understanding. In these work-related incidents, we did not find cases in which people attempted to reconcile discrepant views for the pure sake of achieving a common view. In the situations we have examined, development of shared understanding tends to occur as part of a broader process in which some decision needs to be made.

A second critical assumption is that team members do not merely engage in analytical evaluations of others' arguments. They also judge the credibility of their team members who are proposing those arguments based on recognitional processes. Furthermore, these credibility judgments are at least sometimes based on diagnostic cues, and they serve important functions. In particular, these judgments are invaluable aids in memory management. The number and complexity of arguments that must be processed in a team meeting can induce enormous cognitive demands on the individual members. By relying

on recognition-based judgments of source credibility, a consumer of others' mental models can greatly decrease those demands.

This assumption was also evident in our illustrative case. Specifically, the manager was deeply engaged in digesting and evaluating the theories offered by each of the specialists. Nevertheless, in the end, he confessed to relying heavily on the opinion offered by the flight chief, due to the judged expertise of that senior enlisted man.

Team Decision/Shared Belief

At some point, the resolution process ends. This could occur if the team comes to a consensus on the nature of the situation, or more likely, if time demands dictate that some decision be made. In the latter cases, a pseudo-consensus is achieved, either by the team leader's directive or by capitulation among several disagreeing participants.

In the uncommanded pitch example, a true consensus never emerged during the incident, and indeed is most likely still lacking to this day. In that case, the Manager simply had to call the time for discussion to a close and make a decision.

A second example that illustrates these same points of the model is provided in Table 5. In terms of domain, this is a very different case having to do with intelligence analysis by a multinational team. Nevertheless, as can be seen in Table 5, the key model aspects are strikingly similar. First, the underlying issue pertains to task related differences in mental models. Also, the goals and values of team members are brought to the fore, with consideration of the substantive arguments occurring later in the process. Further, the values and beliefs are highly interdependent, rather than being determined independently. Also, although the team leader attempts to understand the argument presented by the Greek and Turk, he buys in to their account primarily because of the following two credibility cues: 1) these two "natural enemies" share the same view; and 2) each appears to be intimately knowledgeable of the target culture. This incident also highlights that there is at least occasional need for members of the larger team to split off, and attempt to converge on their mental models in a one-on-one fashion.

Table 5

Milosevich Finds Religion

The order came down to the head of the Bosnian analysis team on Sunday morning. The General needed the team to identify the propaganda themes that the Croats, Bosniacs, and Serbs would use by Monday. The team came in on a Sunday to put together a briefing.

The team was multinational, with an American, a Dutch, a Turk, a Greek, and a German officer all working together. The American was the team leader.

They had been studying the issue and background data for about nine weeks. The leader felt the team was in agreement on the correct themes that would be used. In fact, the team had two separate interpretations and analyses of what was happening and what was driving events. This did not surface until dinner on the Sunday that the team was putting the briefing together. The critical difference had to do with the Serbs, and the possibility that Milosevich would switch from Stalinist communism to pursue a religious angle in the upcoming months.

At dinner, the Greek and the Turkish officers got frustrated with the conversations of the others and finally said, 'you don't understand.' The Greek referred to the Turk and said, 'you tell them, they won't believe me.' And the Turkish officer said, 'look the problem is you're thinking secular, and they're not. At this point, the reaction of the others was silence. It was one of those conversation killers. The good news about the silence though was it gave them a chance to press ahead with their reasons that the Serbs would pursue the religious angle. The leader felt that if any of the team objected, the Greek and the Turk would have dropped it because they really did not want to be a problem to the team.

The other members looked at the situation as purely a political process, Milosevich was promising the people who were his natural constituency a better day. They predicted that he would continue to promise a greater Serbia, with the Serbs dominating the political processes and the economic base of whatever was left of Yugoslavia. The Greek and Turk felt that proved he would not be powerful enough to rally Serbs behind him, because there was no passion in that. They said that the only thing passionate in this was the religious separation.

The leader knew the Geek and Turk had been working together. Now he realized that they kept their views to themselves because they didn't think that the others would believe it. But they felt compelled once they had been asked the question about propaganda themes. They felt strongly that missing the religious theme represented a threat to NATO. The Turk said, 'Greece and Serbia have been allies since Byzantine times against Turks and Muslims. If the analysis team made a recommendation that would lead NATO to choose sides, then NATO would put their two countries at each other's throats.

The focus of the argument that the Dutchman had with them was that they really shouldn't worry about their assessment's impact on the member states. The Greek and Turk felt was that with the wall coming down, they should be very wary of issues that might divide the alliance because they no longer had a large enemy to focus on and minor disagreements would now become major. And so that was most of the conversation at dinner.

Table 5 (Continued)

Milosevich Finds Religion

After dinner the leader was approached by the Greek and Turk again, and they took him aside to give their pitch again with a different angle. The team leader listened to them because it struck him as very unusual that people from traditional enemy countries came to the same conclusion and worked together to get the word to him. Also, they had a very good feel for the culture, much better than the rest of the team. The rest had the distant political-analytical perspective, but they had a much closer, more personal, visceral perspective.

The Dutchman also approached the leader alone, and they discussed the proposed. The Dutchman said that it might work, though he didn't believe it. He just didn't believe that a Marxist could get away with taking that line, or that he would have any credibility if he tried. The Dutchman also felt that the nationalist card alone would be enough to get people behind him. His view was that because the Greek and the Turkish disagreement was religious, they saw all conflicts as religious. He said these things to the leader alone, not in front of the Greek and Turk, because he didn't want to insult them. [But he went along with it because he was tired, and he figured, you know, what the hell, it let them fill the slide.]

And then when they got together again that evening as a team, the leader said, 'okay, look, here's what I've got as common themes,' and he included the religious angle for the Serbs. They did three slides, one for each of the contending groups and then left.

In the end, Milosevich did take the religious angle. He made his first connection to religion in this conflict in May of 1992, several weeks after their prediction.

The Added Value of Teams for Developing Understanding

A potentially disturbing aspect of our model and findings is that teams do not appear to achieve real consensus during the shared understanding development process. If consensus is indeed rarely achieved, that raises the question of whether it even makes sense to try developing a shared understanding at all. As illustrated in the example presented in Table 5, the array of backgrounds, experience bases, and the repertoire of mental models within the group as a whole can provide a significant benefit in the team shared understanding development process. For example, Spiro, Feltovich, Coulson, and Anderson (1989) have shown that any single model, any single analogy, can be limiting and misleading as an account of a complex phenomenon. One member of a team may notice and give weight to pieces of data that another team member may neglect. Similarly, one team member may retrieve a different mental model to account for the data that another team member may not have within his collection of mental models. The challenge is to make explicit the tacit knowledge and mental model discrepancies that reside with different members of a team, so as to draw connections between unshared but consistent elements, and resolve conflicting aspects. These pieces of data might not hold significant meaning when considered in isolation, but when considered in combination, they may provide a deeper understanding of the situation. Sharing and fusing data and mental models among team members enables the team to fill in gaps and provide a richer understanding of the situation.

During any type of understanding development process, an inaccurate or erroneous mental model may be retrieved, which affects the search for subsequent data and the interpretation of those data. Individuals can prematurely close or fixate on a potential account of the situation, closing off other potential interpretations of the data. If they are so fixated, they may ignore, overlook, or explain away certain data points that do not fit into their current understanding of the situation. If their mental model is inappropriate or erroneous, this may not be noticed unless the person receives feedback that seriously departs from their current understanding. Attempting to develop shared understanding among team members has the potential to reduce this problem of fixation.

For example, in a study of simulated scientific discoveries, Dunbar (1993) asked participants to attempt to discover how genes control other genes. The simulated environment was based on actual biological models and research, and participants were placed in the same original (and incorrect) hypothesis state as the original biologists at the start of their research. Participants were able to conduct experiments that provided evidence inconsistent with their original hypothesis. At this point, participants dealt with the inconsistent evidence depending on how they set their goals. One group maintained the goal of seeking evidence to support their original hypothesis. None of these participants ever discovered the actual mechanism governing gene regulation. Others instead set a new goal of attempting to explain the cause of the inconsistent findings. These participants tended to generate the correct hypothesis. These, and other findings, led Dunbar to conclude that people's goals determine when and how inconsistent evidence is used. In particular, in the face of inconsistent evidence, when people change their goal to one of determining the cause of unexpected findings, they make discoveries.

Dunbar (1995) extended these findings in a naturalistic study of actual biological scientists working in their laboratories. As in other naturalistic studies, important aspects of the natural situation were the influences of experience and group interactions on individual scientists' handling of inconsistent evidence. In terms of experience, the more experienced scientists were much more willing to let go of their original hypothesis, and set a new goal of understanding the inconsistent findings. The experienced scientists were especially sensitive to inconsistent findings arising in their control conditions, and explicitly thought of control conditions as serving two purposes: checking experimental conditions, and exposing hidden mechanisms. However, the very experienced scientists appeared to display what Dunbar termed a "falsification bias," that is, they would discard good data that actually confirmed their hypothesis.

Group interactions were even more important for determining how scientists would deal with inconsistent or surprising results. In particular, the individual scientists were very unlikely to invent a totally new hypothesis or concept or frame to account for the data. This typically happened during or as a result of laboratory meetings where individuals presented their results to their peers. In these settings, the other scientists tended to focus on the inconsistency and either suggest alternative hypotheses, or force the individual to think of a new hypothesis. Dunbar found this to be a primary mechanism underlying conceptual change. However, it tended to work only when the original researcher did not attribute the results to error. No change occurred when results were attributed to error.

Although there is apparent added value when a team (versus an individual) engages in an understanding development process, the process of sharing and synthesizing the data and accounts from a variety of individuals carries with it increased coordination burdens for teams. Coordination and synthesis can be challenging due to a number of factors including potential information overload, complexity of the information, the emergence of conflicting information, uncertainty regarding the reliability of certain pieces of information, and so on. The burden of coordination is increased further in the face of time pressure. Successful handling of an event entails team members knowing how to elicit the appropriate information and mental model aspects, which information is important to share, how much context to provide while sharing the information, and so on. Success also entails knowing when uncertainty has been reduced sufficiently – i.e., knowing when there is a satisfactory fit between the data and the mental models in order for a decision to be made or for an action to be taken.

IMPLICATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

In this section, we describe requirements for collaborative technologies to support shared understanding development. We then propose tool concepts that aim to support the process, as well as measure the degree of mental model sharedness, especially for teams working under distributed, asynchronous conditions. We then discuss future research directions aimed at further validating the model and tool concepts.

Collaborative Technology Requirements

Based on our findings and model, we propose several features that should reside in a tool to aid distributed teams in developing a shared understanding in high-uncertainty situations: (1) argument as kernel form of representation; (2) flexibility to create arguments pertaining to substantive beliefs or motivational desires, but with a means for denoting which type is being created; (3) allowance for the explicit representation and sharing of the judged credibility of argument sources; (4) process for efficient sharing and comparison of individual team member understanding; (5) consolidation of individual understanding into a representation of the emergent team understanding; (6) individual updating of arguments that permits both divergence and convergence from the team model; (7) capability for subgroups to split off and work out their views away from the rest of the team.

Collaboration Tool Concepts for the Development of Shared Understanding

One possible tool for promoting the development of shared understanding is a concept map. A concept map is a schematic device for representing meaningful relationships among concepts. In a typical map, each concept is enclosed in a circle, with arrows connecting the concepts. The arrows are labeled with the relationships among the concepts. A very simple example is shown in Figure 3. As can be seen, the result is a map depicting the organization of important concepts and their relationships. Concepts maps could thus capture how individual team members are understanding situations in a

graphical form that can be readily shared with others at a distance. However, the fundamental elements of concept maps are concepts and links that together form propositions. Given that we are considering arguments as the fundamental building blocks for our tool, it is likely to be unnecessarily inefficient to explicitly map the elements of propositions.

Figure 3. Example of simple concept map.

An alternative to concept maps is to preserve the general idea of graphically constructing understanding, but to adjust the level of analysis to map the components of arguments (cf. Kirschner, Shum, & Carr, 2003). This approach requires a theory that specifies the elements of arguments in practical or informal (as opposed to purely deductive) reasoning. We describe an approach rooted in the theory of argument proposed by Toulmin (1958). The original purpose of this theory was to provide a means by which arguments could be laid out for rhetorical analysis. Our adapted purpose is to provide a means for clear representation and sharing of understanding, especially for distributed, collaborative analysis. According to Toulmin, an argument is a movement from accepted evidence to a claim, through a warrant. The warrant provides the rationale for relating the evidence to the claim, and is often left implicit. The basic structure and an example are provided in Figure 4, below.

Figure 4. Examples of the basic structure of a warrant.

Recall that warrants are often left implicit in natural communication of understanding. This often appears to lead to confusion in the sharing and evaluation of arguments among

team members. One possible way to handle this situation would be to force their full specification in the argument maps. However, this would increase the cognitive burden associated with creating and digesting the arguments, and the added value of fully specifying warrants is unclear. An alternative approach is to specify the general nature of the warrants. For example, Brockriede and Ehninger (1960) developed a taxonomy that classifies the forms that arguments (actually, argument warrants) can take. For example, a warrant might take the form of a causal link or similarity between parallel cases. Both of these kinds of warrants are substantive in nature. A complete set of substantive warrants is provided below in Table 6. In addition to the substantive forms, warrants could also be based on authority (judged credibility) or motivation. So, again, instead of fully specifying warrants, team members could indicate which type of warrant they are applying for a particular argument.

Table 6

Kinds of Substantive Warrants (Brockreide & Ehninger, 1960)

Warrant Type	Description
Cause	Causal link between evidence and claim
Sign	Covariation without the causal link
Generalization	Induction from a sample to a population
Classification	Concluding from the general population to a specific instance
Parallel case	Concluding based on a similarity between instances
Analogy	Concluding based on a similarity of relationship with something outside of the domain

In addition to the three central components of the argument, Toulmin (1958) also specified a second set of components which may or may not apply in a given situation. These are called the backing, rebuttal, and qualifier. Backing consists of additional support that can bolster the warrant. Rebuttals specify the boundary conditions on the argument, and qualifiers convey the degree of certainty in the argument. The full structure that contains all of these elements is presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Central components of the argument.

Collaborative Argument Mapping Tool Concept

We envision a tool where individual team members can create and share very flexible argument maps to represent their understanding. For our purposes, the Toulmin (1958) theory, along with the extensions of warrants by Brockriede and Ehniger (1960), provide basic building blocks for building the maps. Individuals can select nodes that correspond to the Toulmin elements (e.g., evidence node, claim node, etc.), and can join these nodes by choosing links reflecting the distinct kinds of warrants: motivational, authority, and the various substantive warrants. Team members can share, scrutinize, and respond to each other's argument maps. Backing and rebuttals, in particular, provide mechanisms for input into other team members' arguments. For example, suppose that one teammate had produced the Russia example presented above. In a response, another team member could select a rebuttal node and use it to challenge the first member's evidence.

This tool concept also requires the specification of a process by which team members can share and respond to each others' arguments in a somewhat systematic manner. The development and testing of an appropriate team process will need to be completed in Phase II. Our overarching goal in developing a collaboration process for the argument mapping tool will be to provide the flexibility for team members to engage in the kinds of resolution activities that they perform naturally in face-to-face settings.

Note that our use of the Toulmin (1958) theory diverges considerably from its initial intent, or ways in which it has been adopted by others. The original intent of the Toulmin framework was to aid the rhetorical analysis of arguments presented by a single source. Elements of the framework, such as backing, rebuttals, and qualifiers have thus been associated with ways that the individual source anticipated potential objections to their argument. In this capacity, the theoretical constructs are typically incorporated in a template format. The templates display all the elements presented in Figure 5, in a rigidly structured fashion essentially as shown in that figure. For example, (Cheikes, Lehner, Adelman, & Taylor, 2004) conducted an experimental study to evaluate the effectiveness of this kind of a template intervention. They gave participants articles and asked them to fill out blank templates with information presented therein. In this study, mixed support was found for improved analysis of the articles using the templates.

Our suggested usage contrasts with the standard approach in at least two ways. First, we do not suggest using the Toulmin argument elements in a restrictive, template format. Instead, our tool will provide nodes that correspond to the elements, but the nodes can be combined flexibly. Second, our tool concept specifically encourages people to develop and share their own arguments in a collaborative environment. Indeed, we see it as a collaborative environment first, with argument mapping as a specific feature.

Metrics for Shared Understanding

Creating and sharing argument maps may prove a valuable means for developing a shared understanding of ambiguous situations, especially among distributed and

asynchronous teams. The argument maps themselves might additionally provide useful representations for gauging the extent of shared understanding. For example, consider a set of team members, each of whom develops their own argument map independently. That might be a good first step in the collaborative understanding development process. Metrics for degree of shared understanding could also be derived by analytical comparison of the individual maps. The general idea is to construct measures of the similarity between different individuals' argument maps. If done appropriately, the measures of map similarity would provide the metrics for shared understanding. Approaches for describing the similarity between two maps are discussed next. These should be worked out as a first step, followed by extension to the case with $n > 2$ maps.

A relatively simple approach for measuring the similarity between two maps follows from Tversky's "features of similarity" model (1977). According to this model, the similarity between two objects (A and B) can be computed as a weighted linear function of three components: the number of common elemental features, the number of features in A but not in B, and the number of features in B but not in A. In argument maps, the basic features are the proposition nodes that collectively form arguments, and the links between those nodes. So, a set of metrics that at least partially captures shared understanding would be the number of shared nodes and links, and the two kinds of distinctive nodes and links, with a linear combination forming the aggregate metric.

Rowe and Cook (1995) developed an approach to measure the similarity between concept maps that is related to Tversky's model. Specifically, they computed the proportion of nodes and links shared between two concept maps as a measure of concept map similarity. In both cases, similarity is determined by common and distinctive atomic features. A distinction is that Tversky's linear combination would assign higher similarity scores to more highly detailed shared maps, whereas the proportion measure does not account for map complexity in its scores.

Another approach would build off of "structure-mapping theory" to develop shared understanding metrics that take into account the full structure of the arguments, in addition to the bottom level features. The "features" approach, utilized by Tversky (1977), as well as Rowe and Cook (1995), captures the similarity between maps at an atomic level, but misses the similarities and dissimilarities that exist at higher levels. Gentner's (1983) structure-mapping theory provides some guidance on how higher-level similarity between maps might be included. Within structure-mapping theory, situations are characterized by systems composed of individual objects and their attributes, first-order relations (FRs) between the objects, and higher-order relations (HRs) between FRs (or other HRs). For example, "x is red" is an attribute, with the object being whatever fills in for x. Also for example, "x attacks y" and "y flees from x" are both FRs. An example of a second-order HR would be {"x attacks y" causes "y flees from x"}. The complexity obviously increases dramatically with increases in the HR order. A fundamental principle of structure-mapping theory is the *systematicity principle*, which states that systems of predicates containing HRs are mapped first, constraining the common lower order relations. That is, there is a defined process by which two relational systems can be compared, and their similarity computed. Algorithms for this approach are sophisticated,

but the needed computational formalisms have been developed for general situations. What would be needed is an adaptation of the general approach to deal with argument maps, specifically.

In terms of the argument maps, the individual proposition nodes will tend to be objects and attributes, or FRs. An argument will consist of a system of higher-order relations. The general idea is that two maps, each of which contains very complex arguments, may share many common nodes, but convey quite different meanings due to differences in how those nodes are utilized in the arguments. On the other hand, if two sophisticated arguments share close relational correspondences (in addition to common nodes), then their creators can be said to have developed a very closely shared understanding of the situation.

Comparison with Other Ongoing Developments

O'Connor, Johnson, and Khalil (2004) reported developments of an analytical method for constructing a "shared" concept map based on individual concept maps generated by individual team members. The approach returns a concept map that reflects the common elements and relational clusters pulled from across a set of team members' individual maps. This approach shares some basic assumptions with our collaborative argument mapping notions. Two specific shared ideas are that concept or argument maps provide useful external representations of mental models, and that having individual team members generate them is a useful first step towards developing a shared mental model. However, a key difference is that our aim is to provide a tool that facilitates team members' efforts to develop their own understanding. In contrast, the O'Connor, et al. approach is to have the researchers construct a representation of a shared concept map/mental model based on the inputs of individual team members.

Our approach also bears some superficial similarities with structured argumentation tools, such as the Structured Evidential Argumentation System (SEAS) (Lowrance, Harrison, & Rodriguez, 2001). For example, at a high level, both approaches attempt to provide argumentation support to aid the development of understanding. However, there are at least two critical differences. One is that SEAS is primarily intended to support individuals, though it may allow some limited sharing of data. Our argument mapping tool concept, is first and foremost a collaborative understanding development tool. The idea is to provide a means to facilitate the sharing of mental models. The graphical representations seek to improve the conveyance of arguments, and especially the coordination and tracking of rebuttals and counter-arguments between distributed, asynchronous team members.

A second distinction is that, as noted by Lowrance et al. (2001), SEAS provides users with queries based on preformed templates. Users simply fill in the templates with the requested information, and also report multiple-choice confidence judgments that the information is correct. The entries and judgments are then used by the system to derive a conclusion for the analyst. Our argument mapping tool concept differs from SEAS in that it supports users in building their understanding, as opposed to having the system attempt

to put the pieces together for them. This difference highlights an important attitudinal distinction, consistent with our view of users as actively-engaged in making sense of the situation, as opposed to users as relatively passive agents that feed data into systems for processing.

Summary

In summary, based on a model of how collocated teams construct their shared understanding in uncertain situations, we have developed requirements for technology to promote shared understanding development among members of distributed teams. The initial concept of an “argument map” as a tool for representing and sharing understanding has also been described. This tool concept meets the basic requirements, and appears to provide additional support to the process, as follows:

- Reduces memory demands by visually displaying arguments, rather than relying on verbal exchange.
- Enables critical examination by clearly laying out the full argument components for scrutiny.
- Maintains the flexibility inherent in natural exchanges, by allowing values, beliefs, and even source credibility to be communicated.
- Is based on a dynamic, rather than static conception of argument, and can provide for the iterated construction of a shared map representing emergent team understanding.

The primary purpose of the argument map is to provide a means for displaying and communicating understanding. However, the nature of the map representation allows for the development of metrics to assess shared understanding, based on measures of the similarity between individually created maps.

Directions for Further Research

Thus far, we have described initial research, a resulting model of shared understanding development, and tool concepts based on the model that aim to support and measure collaborative understanding development. In this section, we discuss further research that is needed to assure the development of an effective solution.

One critical research need is to improve our understanding of the intuitive aspects of the natural process. Specifically, we have found intuitive credibility judgments to be at least as important as substantive argument content when team members decide whether or not to “buy” each others’ mental models. Critical questions remaining here include: In what team decision making situations do credibility judgment heuristics work well, and where do they lead to problems? Does it really make sense to push towards a pure focus on substance? Is it actually possible to do it—or do you just trade one set of heuristics for another?

Another primary area for further research pertains to the influence of cultural differences on team members' understanding. Cultural differences could affect the understanding process in a couple of important ways. One stage in the model that may be culturally dependent is the Team Resolution Process. Specifically, the generation and sharing of arguments, rebuttals, and counterarguments among team members may happen in very different ways depending on culture. In most Western cultures, engaging in argumentation and debate is viewed positively. It's a way for team members to express differing viewpoints and to ultimately improve team performance. However, the open display of contrasting opinions that is central to the Western concepts of discussion and debate tends to be uncomfortable for cultural groups who place a higher value on harmony and on maintaining honor (Feghali, 1997; Patai, 2002). In East Asian and Middle Eastern cultures, for example, conflict is viewed primarily as a damaging force and is avoided. Team members tend to be more reticent about expressing their viewpoints. If they have opinions that are different from other team members, they may not voice those discrepancies at all. They may even express agreement with their team members, providing a false sense of shared understanding. If they do voice disagreements, it will be in private. Doing so in public risks causing loss of face for a fellow team member or damage to interpersonal relations (McHugh, Smith, Klinger, & O'Dea, 2004).

The process of judging the credibility of arguments presented by team members is also likely to be influenced by cultural factors, such as the dimension of Power Distance (Hofstede, 1980, 2001). Power Distance reflects differences in interpersonal power between superior and subordinate team members (Hofstede, 1980). People with low Power Distance show egalitarian working patterns and team interchanges. They judge others on merit not rank. Those in high power distance cultures, however, tend to judge others based on rank and status. In cultures high in Power Distance, one's status or level of authority may be given substantially more weight as a credibility cue. Judgments of credibility are likely to be influenced by this cultural factor and others.

CONCLUSION

The primary goal for this SBIR Phase I project was to develop a cognitive process model of how teams attempt to construct a shared understanding in the face of a surprise or anomaly. The premise is that in order to build effective tools to support distributed, asynchronous collaborative understanding construction, we first need to develop a deep understanding of the natural process. The risk of attempting to support that process without understanding how it works is that critical aspects of the process may actually be rendered ineffective by the system. This can lead to failure to achieve the fullest benefits from the aid, or actually lead to degraded performance. It can also lead to frustration and abandonment of the systems by the intended users. On the other hand, support tools that are designed with an intimate understanding of the cognitive processes in mind are much more likely to be accepted and provide real support.

Hence, as a part of the Phase I effort, we developed a model of how teams construct a shared understanding in the face of uncertainty. One feature of the model is that team

members often attempt to share their individual, complex mental models of the situation by producing and consuming each others' summary arguments. The arguments may pertain to substantive beliefs or motivational desires, and the two are very much intermixed in the process of coming to an understanding (as opposed to desires being treated as independent and irrelevant to belief formation). In fact, it sometimes seems that motivations and desires are used to constrain the space encompassing what beliefs to construct. Hence, this motivational bias may serve an important function for reducing cognitive load. In addition to the central content that is shared, there is also another, typically private, level at which evaluations are being made. Specifically, team members are deciding how critical to be of others' arguments, based in part on the judged credibility of the person(s) presenting them. We propose that the credibility judgments greatly reduce the cognitive burdens associated with evaluating and remembering all of the different and potentially quite complicated arguments.

The model we developed in Phase I represents a significant advance in understanding how teams develop shared understanding in natural settings. We are excited to push forward to develop and test our proposed collaborative solutions based on the model in the Phase II project. To that end, we proposed tool requirements and concepts that aim to support the process, especially for teams working under distributed, asynchronous conditions. Specifically, we proposed to develop a collaborative tool that allows people to visually map out their mental models as arguments, and then share and review the argument maps with their teammates. We also proposed how metrics for shared understanding could be computed based on the same general tool concept. Finally, we discussed further research directions aimed at further validating the model and tool concepts.

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APPENDIX A.

Interview Guide for Team Development of Shared Understanding

Incident Identification

Can you think of a time when...

- you had a hard time understanding a teammate's point of view?
- there was a lot of confusion or disagreement among your team, and you wished your team could just do a "mind-meld" to straighten things out?
- members of your team had very different opinions about how to interpret a situation?
- you thought your team was in sync, but then you realized that they were not?

Listen for an incident that fits your study goals, and where participant played a key/leadership role.

Team Formation

Who were the main players on this team?

Timeline Verification

Will you give me a quick run through the incident?
How long was the incident from start to resolution?

Listen for: Group decision points, team "checks" on understanding, breakdowns in common ground, anomalies/violated expectancies (about the team or that the team had to deal with), changes in understanding among at least some team members.

Deepening

What was it that let you know what was going on?
How did you know what information to share?
What led you to accept (or reject) what [team member X] had to say?
What information did you think was significant before [the critical event]?
What was the team's understanding before [the critical event]?
Where did [each player] line up on the issue?
What were some of the other theories discussed?
What led your team to prefer the chosen alternative over others?
What about the situation let the team know that the members' understanding was inaccurate or that opinions differed?
What did the team do to recover their understanding or get back in sync?
What questions did you or other members of the team have at this time?
How did you all go about finding the answers?
What information did the team miss or not pay as much attention to as they should have?

What If Queries

What if the team members had been distributed (collocated) – how would that have changed things?

What if you had all the time needed to regroup/re-form your team before moving on with the task—what would you have done?

If there was one piece of information the team could have shared at this point, what would it be?

What if information coming from a particular team member suddenly stopped?